

«THE IMPORTANCE OF GRAMMAR IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE»

Odilova Gulchiroy Husniddin qizi

student of Andijan state institute of foreign languages, group 418

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7179283>

Abstract. The grammar intended for teaching the mother tongue serves primarily to help the student realize, systematize or understand what he, in most cases, correctly uses grammar before learning grammar, practically based on his “linguistic instinct”. When studying a foreign language, a student, in contrast to a native speaker of that language, at first does not have any “competence” in the studied foreign language. Therefore, a grammar intended for teaching a foreign language, in no case can not rely on linguistic flair and should accordingly contain explicit rules for the formation and use of grammatical forms and structures of a foreign language.

Key words: grammar rules, foreign languages, grammatical forms, fundamental tool, phrases and word groups.

It is a fact that grammar has the most important role in learning any foreign language. If we do not know grammar rules, we cannot make sentences without mistakes. Likewise, we can say that grammar is the foundation of the language that we are learning. We should start to learn a foreign language with mastering grammar. After learning grammar rules by heart we can continue to acquire knowledge of other skills: reading, speaking, listening.

Grammar helps to make it clear to the reader what is being expressed. It is a fundamental tool in good writing, as incorrect grammar can radically alter the meaning of that which is written. Grammar helps to make it clear to the reader what is being expressed. It is a fundamental tool in good writing, as incorrect grammar can radically alter the meaning of that which is written. Basic grammatical systems have been in place since as early as the Elizabethan era, and have not really changed very much in terms of their fundamental rules and precepts. Whereas time has seen the ever-changing nature of many other aspects of the English language, such as usage, the meanings of words, and spellings. Another thing to mention is that learning appropriate grammar is essential because it is the language that makes it viable for us to effectively speak about language. Grammar names the phrases and word groups that make up sentences no longer solely in English but in nearly any language. As humans, we can put sentences together even as children. But to be in a position to discuss about how sentences are built, about the sorts of phrases and word companies that make up sentences—that is understanding grammar. With this,

understanding about grammar opens a window into the human mind and into our amazingly complicated intellectual capacity of understanding and studying a unique language. We usually companion grammar with mistakes and correctness. But preserve in mind, knowing about grammar also helps us recognize what makes sentences and paragraphs clear and interesting, excellent and precise.

I strongly believe that language learners will pay a great deal of attention to learn grammar productively by reading this article. Likewise, I recommend them to study grammatic rules of the language they are learning as the first step. As a result they will master any foreign language quickly and effectively.

References:

1. https://www.grammar.com/the_role_of_grammar_in_learning_foreign_languages
2. <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.teflcourse.net/amp/blog/the-importance-oflearning-grammar-ittt-tefl-blog>